

Role of Disability Activists to Enhance Employment Equity for Person with Disabilities (Studyat Difabel Mandiri Indonesia Foundation)

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the efforts of disability activists at the Difabel Mandiri Indonesia Foundation (DMIF) in providing access to disabled workers and to find out the obstacles experienced by persons with disabilities to work in the formal sector. This research was conducted using a qualitative approach with a descriptive research type. Data was collected using in-depth interview techniques involving two disability activists, four persons with disabilities, one staff of the Tangerang City Social Service, and one employer. The study results find that disability activists in DMIF play a facilitating role, an educational role, a representational role, and a technical role. The obstacles faced are personal and environmental factors.

Keywords: DMIF, Person with Disabilities, Community Worker

I. INTRODUCTION

The issue of disability is still a global issue that has gained international attention. Disability is an issue that (should be) very “familiar” to the public because it is part of the human condition. Almost every individual has experienced a disability at some stage of their life. For people who reach a long life, they will likely experience difficulties related to their physical and social functioning (WHO, 2011, p. 3). The International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) states that disabilities are disorders experienced by humans in carrying out their functions which are divided into three related categories, namely "impairments", "activity limitations", and "participation restrictions." (WHO, 2011, p. 5). One of the barriers experienced by PWD is access to employment. According to the ICF, impairments include problems with body functions or structures, such as blindness and paralysis. Activity limitations are when a person has trouble in activities such as difficulty walking or eating. Whereas what is meant by participation restrictions are people who experience social activity problems, for example, experiencing discrimination in getting a job and accessibility to public transportation.

In the Disability and Development Report issued by the UN Agency in 2018, the workforce ratio to population or employment to population ratio (EPR) of PWD aged 15 years and over is still low at 36%, while non-PD EPR is 60%. This data shows that the opportunity for persons with disabilities to get a job is lower than for non-disabled people. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, according to the results of the National Socio-Economic Survey (Susenas) in 2018, the number of people with disabilities over the age of two is 31.2 million people (12.29%). Meanwhile, 19.7 million persons with disabilities fall into the productive age group (15-64 years) (refer to Table 1). It reflects that there are 19.7 PWD who need attention in order to get the same work opportunities as other citizens.

Table 1. Data of Number of People with Disabilities by Group

		Number of PwD	Total Population	Percentage PwD
	Total PwDs in Indonesia > 2 years	31.242.233	254.303.480	12.29%
1.	Children with disabilities (2 – 17 years)	3.147.148	75.038.048	4.19%
2.	Productive age (15 – 64 years)	19.788.682	177.882.094	11.12%
3.	Elderly	8.706.305	15.204.477	57.26%

Source : Working Paper of SMERU 2020

The Indonesian government guarantees the protection of the right of PwD to obtain a job through Law No. 8 of 2016 concerning Persons with Disabilities. Article 53 specifically mentioned the quota for disability workers in all sectors, namely the government, local governments, State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), and Regional Owned Enterprises (BUMD), which are required to employ at least 2 percent of PD of the number of employees or workers. Meanwhile, private companies must employ PD at least 1 percent of the total number of workers. There is an award given by the government for companies that accept PD workers. However, there has been no apparent sanction issued by the government or court for companies that do not provide employment opportunities for disability workers. As a result, even though there are legal umbrella and technical guidelines regarding the absorption of disability workers in Indonesia, PwD's accessibility to work in the formal sector still limited.

Social welfare conditions achieve when social problems can be managed, social needs are met, and opportunities to improve human social conditions are available. High crime, unemployment, poverty, and other social problems indicate decreasing social welfare (Midgley, 1995). One of the efforts to realize social welfare with a social development approach is an approach to improve community welfare that is suitable not only to improve the quality of life of all citizens but also to respond to distorted development problems.

The lack of job opportunities and frequent rejection experienced by PwD often make them despair. Besides the government and private sector, there is a need for nonprofits organizations such as organizations of persons with disabilities (OPD) to overcome social problems such as difficulty in access to jobs. Berman (2002) said, "Nonprofits play a pivotal role in addressing challenging societal problems and improving the quality of life for all" (p. 10). Meanwhile, Renz (2010) said, "the nonprofit sector fills gaps that are not handled by the business and government sectors." (Walters, 2020).

It is hoped that the role of persons with disabilities organizations can bring change and can overcome social problems that are often faced by PwD to improve their welfare. Ife (1997, p. 53) states that the agents of change play a role as community workers or enablers. Ife (2013) further argues that community workers are seen as activities or practices of someone who facilitates the process of finding the needs of human life, either paid or not to do the job. Anti Mutiah & Astuti (2018) researched in Difabel Friends Community to describe the organization's role as a Community-based Organization. The results are to inspire by building self-confidence in all its members; convey information directly or indirectly to all members; and establish good communication (improve) with the government and be open to anyone who invites cooperation, either the government or the private sector. Meanwhile, Armstrong et al. (1993) reported on the role of OPDs in increasing employment opportunities for persons with disabilities by encouraging those with group skills (for example, sewing skills, radio or TV repair) to train other members as their apprentices, providing them with job placements after training.

II. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

One of the organizations of persons with disabilities that strives for persons with disabilities to function socially and improve their welfare is the Difabel Mandiri Indonesia Foundation (DMIF) in Tangerang. It stems from a community on the Facebook Social Network called the Komunitas Penyandang Disabilitas Indonesia (KPDI). Most of the members are people with disabilities who want to share what experiences they face amid society with all its problems, such as the lack of job vacancies, demanding access to education, and lack of skills for persons with disabilities to enter the formal and informal work sectors. An idea arose to form a foundation, which manages

coaching and assistance for people with disabilities, which is more organized. It hopes to be part of a program to improve the welfare of persons with disabilities whose fate is still less fortunate compared to society in general. DMIF is also a forum for persons with disabilities to interact with each other and express their aspirations because they see that there are still many problems in the field. Also, disability activists at DMIF act as agents of change who seek to change the discourse experienced by persons with disabilities, such as the lack of job vacancies, demanding access to education, and lack of skills for persons with disabilities to enter the formal and informal work sectors. The benefits of this disability activist's efforts came from the interviews, "I know DMIF start in 2013, 2014. I only know from social media. It said the foundation for disabilities. I looked for opportunities to work because I wanted to work. I read its vision and mission. They tried to find out how people with disabilities had the opportunity to make a useful contribution to their family and company. They provide opportunities for businesses, too, to work in the company by bridging their impressions. It is beneficial." (KI, person with disability).

The interview results above show that DMIF has made efforts so that people with disabilities have the individual ability to do their life tasks properly so that they can fulfill their daily needs and improve their welfare. DMIF plays an active role in providing accessibility for persons with disabilities to work in the formal sector by developing the skills and capacities of persons with disabilities to carry out their social roles and functions in social life. DMIF assists in fulfilling and protecting the rights of persons with disabilities, such as job opportunities, education, health, and advocacy, and encouragement of the need to realize protection and accessibility for persons with disabilities. Seeing the problems faced by persons with disabilities and the existence of DMIF as an agent of change that seeks to provide accessibility for persons with disabilities to work in the formal sector, the questions formulated for this study are:

- a. What is the role of disability activists at Yayasan Difabel Mandiri Indonesia in providing person with disability with access to work in the formal sector?
- b. What obstacles do they experience in getting a job in the formal sector?

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative approach. Creswell states that qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem (Creswell 2014). This research is descriptive research that aims to explore in-depth information about the accessibility of PWD in finding work, especially in the formal sector. Data collection includes primary and secondary data carried out through literature studies, documentation, and in-depth interviews. In-depth interviews were conducted with two disability activists, five persons with disabilities, and one staff from Tangerang City Social Service staff.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Midgley (1995) said social welfare is a state or condition of human well-being that exist when social problems are managed, when humans are met and when social opportunities are maximized. However, creating a conducive environment for PD cannot do it alone (WHO, 2011). It requires the cooperation of all parties, including organizations of persons with disabilities (OPD), to overcome PD's social problems. This research discusses how the role of disability activists in supporting the efforts of disabled workers in obtaining jobs in the formal sector and the obstacles faced by PWD when applying for jobs. With the existing limitations, it is still difficult for PWD to access their right to get a job, and when they join the OPD, hopefully, they can help access the right to work. When PWD gets a job, it can improve their welfare. According to Spergel (1975), Zastrow (2010), and Adi (2013), when working with individuals, groups, or communities, community workers are expected to have at least the following roles (Adi, 2013, p. 216):

1. Enabler helps individuals or groups convey their needs, assess and identify their problems, explore problem-solving strategies, select and implement strategies, and develop their capacity to deal with problems more effectively. The four primary functions performed as an enabler are:

- a. Helping people realize and see their condition
 - b. Generating and developing "organization" in society
 - c. Develop good interpersonal relationships
 - d. Facilitates effective planning
2. Brokers, which assist the target in connecting with available service sources according to target needs, for example, with community service providers in this case; The Office of Social Affairs and Community Empowerment, as well as the Government, in order to provide services to targets who need assistance or community services.
3. Educators, namely, can convey information correctly and adequately and readily accepted by individuals, groups, and communities who are the target of change.
4. Experts, namely providing input, suggestions, and support for information in various areas.
5. Social planners (social planner), namely collecting data on social problems faced by individuals, groups, and society, analyzing and presenting rational alternative actions in accessing the existing source system to solve the problem of meeting target needs.
6. Advocate, namely as a defender and a representative who defends the interests of the target.
7. Activist is a driving force for the community to carry out an activity.

Ife (2013, p. 306-325) divides community workers' role in community work into four groups according to the table below.

Table 2. Community Work Roles by Ife (2013)

Facilitative	Educational	Representational	Technical
a. Personal communication	a. Consciousness-raising	a. Resources	a. Research
b. Skills & resources	b. Informing	b. Advocacy	b. Computers
c. Group facilitation	c. Confronting	c. Sharing knowledge & experience	c. Presentation
d. Social animation	d. Training	d. Media	d. Management
e. Mediation		e. Public relations	e. Financial control
f. Support		f. Networking	
g. Consensus			
h. Organizing			

A. DMIF's Efforts to Provide Access for People with Disabilities to Work in the Formal Sector

1. Facilitative Role

This role is related to the position of the community work as a facilitator. This role focuses on arousing enthusiasm and supporting community development (Ife, 2013). The roles of disability activists DMIF include providing motivation and inspiration for PWD, monitoring people with disabilities who are already working, providing recommendations, and developing good interpersonal relationships.

1.1 Provide Motivation and Inspiration

The interview results found that the role of disability activists in DMIF is as an enabler. Adi (2013) explains that community workers' role when working with individuals, groups, or communities is to generate and develop an 'organization' in society, awakening the abilities of persons with disabilities. This role stated in one of the foundation's goals, to provide new motivation for PD to continue to exist and survive. Retief & Letšosa (2018) say PwDs should play their role as 'sick person' if they still want to receive help. Persons with disabilities are seen as the source of the problem and see them as weak and helpless human beings. Their role in society is limited, especially children with disabilities who think their life cannot change and can only accept help from other people for the rest of their lives. This limitation makes them insecure. Therefore, disability activists provide motivation and become a source of inspiration for all PWD in this community. In their efforts, disability activists try to build self-confidence by providing materials and presenting resource persons, namely people with disabilities who have successfully run businesses, to share their experiences before the training session begins.

One of the persons with disabilities also mentioned that the founder of DMIF, a person with physical disabilities, was also a source of his motivation to have enthusiasm, courage, and mentality to advance.

"I am motivated by Pak Bandi himself. The same as me, Pak Bandi's condition has difficulty to walk, but he could establish DMIF and help other PwDs. I have enthusiasm, courage, mentality to going forward because of Pak Bandi. He inspires me." (EN, Person with disabilities)

Toseland and Rivas (1984) in Adi (2013: 180-181) state that community workers are a powerful social change source and become role models and resources to overcome social and political pressures. Other informants agreed that disability activists become a source of motivation for other PwDs, including herself. She said:

"I was asked to participate in this event on behalf of DMIF. Pak Bandi gave me the confidence to get involved. At that time, the festival was in Jakarta. I do not dare to go alone. However, Mr. Bandi told me to try it; do not be afraid. He said, 'I can do it, you could do it too'. I got brave and went to Jakarta by myself. When I arrived, I saw friends who participate in festival events are rarely people with disabilities, mostly non-disabled. However, they are welcome and happily talk with me. The festival event went smoothly, and I am happy that I made new friends." (TU, Person with disabilities)

At first, she was afraid to participate in activities carried out by DMIF. However, after seeing the independence of activists with disabilities and getting the encouragement to dare to try, finally, she dared to go alone to the place of activity. She was confident to communicate with non-disabled friends too. It shows that DMIF is doing its part by motivating PwDs to overcome their insecurity. After people with disabilities are confident, they will start to attempt doing activities in society. Disability activists also other PwDs get the same motivation and have the spirit to move forward by joining this community.

1.2 Monitoring Persons with Disabilities Who Have Worked

Another facilitative role is providing support. Community workers play a role in strengthening individuals and are ready if anyone wants to discuss by communicating with people with disabilities (Ife, 2013).

"Pak Bandi often ask, 'how is the job? Comfortable? Any problems? ' If there is time, Pak Bandi likes to come to the office to see the working environment too." (TU, Person with disabilities)

Disability activists keep in touch with PwDs who are already working. They trust them by sharing stories about the difficulties or obstacles at work or personal problems. If there is a chance, disability activists also visit their workplace to see the conditions and facilities.

1.3 Giving Recommendations to Work

It is the ability to see the potential that exists in an individual (Ife, 2013). For example, PwDs who can do

administration, disability activists will proactively recommend them to the employers.

For example, there used to be Dede, Tuti, who can do an administrative job. We recommend them to the employer because we see the capacity. They are working now—Deden in Alfamart office and Tuti in a printing company. (SB, Disability Activist)

Disability activists can give recommendations if PwDs actively participate in activities and programs conducted by DMIF. They can see firsthand the abilities of PwD and recommend it to the company directly if the vacancies offered are per their capacity.

1.4 Visiting Persons with Disabilities and Families

Ife (2013) explains that community workers must also have interpersonal communication skills with all society levels, including families from PwD. This ability is also mentioned by Adi (2013) as an aspect of the enabler's role. Based on the interview results, disability activists have interpersonal communication skills with all levels of society. The problem faced by activists is the low participation of PwDs in the training activities. Disability activists visited PwDs and families to find out the problems.

"We visit and share the importance of PwDs to join our program, attend training, and develop their abilities, especially those who are close to the DMIF office. So, providing advocacy is not only for the PwDs themselves but also for their families. For example, 'please support your child to get capacity building and meet others. Both of you now live, but how about when you are pass away. They cannot always rely on their parents.' So, we share this kind of awareness. They cannot rely on their families all the time. They must be independent. (SB, Disability Activist)

The impact of the activities carried out by the DMIF disability activist was as expressed by the staff of the Social Office in Tangerang:

I once took a sample, in Mekarsari village, there were about 14 disabled people with disabilities, and I have collected an average of only two people who can read; most of them cannot read. I asked them why they could not read. They say special schools are expensive. Second, their parents do not allow them to go to school. Therefore, disability activists at DMIF visited families with disabilities. There are a lot of successful ones, for example, Tuti. She is severely disabled. At first, she did not want to leave the house, did not want to hang out, and then her family did not allow Tuti to do activities outside the house. Pak Bandi often visits and shares. Finally, she could go to school, continue to study in college, and now start teaching. (AF, Staff of Social Office)

One of the objectives of implementing social welfare in Law Number 11 of 2009 concerning Social Welfare is to restore social functions to achieve the independence of individuals with disabilities. Social function is a person's ability to carry out his social functions and roles in carrying out his life tasks according to social status (Raharjo, 2017). The social function can be said to be someone's hope to carry out life's tasks both amid family and society to meet their physical, personal, emotional, and self-concept needs. In this case, persons with disabilities also have the same expectations to carry out their social functions and roles in the family and community.

II. Educational Role

According to Ife (2013), the educational role is the ability of community workers to provide positive and directive input from their knowledge, skills, and experiences. Efforts made by disability activists include increasing employer awareness, providing information on job vacancies and training, and conducting training.

2.1 Increase Employer Awareness

Ife (2013) states that this role can be carried out by increasing awareness in a structured manner and making social change strategies. Robbins, Chatterjee, & Canda (2012) said that the oppression of persons with disabilities is socially constructed so that clients cannot participate fully, and their rights are neglected. Social barriers and

discrimination from society make PwD unable to get the rights and carry out the same obligations as other human beings. It means that what needs to be changed is the people's perspective or stigma on PwD. Disability activists perform this role by building awareness of the importance of work for PwD to employers by having casual discussions with employer management. Disability activists give an understanding that PwD cannot always depend on their parents. To live independently, they must be allowed to work.

We do have an individual strategy to approach it while drinking coffee. Chat from the heart to heart and affect the employer by understanding that people with disabilities are also human. They need to continue their descent and need to live. When those parents are still there, okay, the parents are responsible. However, if the parents are gone, who will be responsible? They will continue to depend on other people for their lives if they cannot be independent. It is not only in terms of the law but also from the human side. What if they are in a position of persons with disabilities? Without a stable job and now pandemic. They understand what friends with disabilities need, but we must talk to the right people, such as HRD managers, General Managers, and owner. (IR, Disability Activist)

If needed, disability activists are also involved in the PwD recruitment process and ensure that the principle of non-discrimination is applied. They are also involved in the adaptation process in the workplace to build good communication between workers. Because employers still do not understand how to handle workers with a disability. The ILO (2013, pp. 38-59) explains that an active role for employers and other parties is needed in the management of disabled workers. This is to ensure that PwD are given access to work according to their abilities, work capacities and interests. In this case, disability activists play an active role in ensuring that PwD can work in a disability-friendly environment and do their duties well.

2.2 Providing Job Vacancies and Training Information

Disability activist also provides information on work support assistance needed by PwD. Ife (2013) states that the meaning of providing the information is the ability to share useful information for the community to fulfill its needs, such as information about programs in other communities and external resources. Adi (2013) categorizes this role as an educator where the community worker provides excellent and correct information. The results showed that disability activists played this role, among others, by providing information about odd-even stickers and their requirements, then directing them to parties who could help to get the stickers. With this sticker, the car can freely pass in odd-even areas and will not be penalized.

Persons with disabilities have the same right to live independently from an economic perspective to fulfill their needs and family's needs. To make it happen, they must work and earn income. Efforts made by disability activists provide job vacancy information through social media such as Whatsapp and Facebook groups.

"DMIF was a community group on Facebook. Hence, until now, we still use social media as a mediator for activities. We also have a WhatsApp group. We share job information and training through these social media". (SB, Disability Activist)

What was stated by the disability activist was agreed upon by persons with disabilities who are members of DMIF. One of the informants said:

"One of DMIF's visions is to channel job opportunities. If there is information about job vacancies, share it with the WA group, Facebook. Mr. Bandi will also have a private chat and say there is an opportunity; there is a job opening." (KI, Person with disabilities)

According to the UN Decade on Disability at the Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP) in 1991 proposed two types of roles for DPOs, namely (1) Information provision, advocacy and lobbying activities related to disability issues; (2) Providing special services to its members (Deepak et al., 2013). Disability activists carry out their roles in line with the concept of OPD roles conveyed by ESCAP by providing information about job opportunities, training activities, and other information supporting PwD to do their activities. DMIF

disability activists actively provide information through Whatsapp groups and other social media such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter as a means of communication.

2.3 Held Capacity Building Activity

Another aspect of the educational role is conducting training by teaching individuals or groups on how to do something (Ife, 2013). One of DMIF goals is to organize empowerment activities or training that help PwDs meet their daily needs by working or doing entrepreneurship. Disability activists carry out this role by holding empowerment activities such as screen-printing training, quail egg farming, computer use, and coffee making.

"I have not had the chance to participate directly, but at DMIF, there is much training, from quail egg farming to computer training." (DN, Person with Disability)

In conducting training, activists with disabilities do not directly train friends with disabilities but find sources to provide learning materials such as those from the Social Office. Ife (2013) explains in more detail that community workers may not act as trainers but rather help groups find resources and resource persons.

"The support is not to us, but for PwDs who are under our guidance. For example, the Social Office has programs such as a capacity-building. They usually contact us to hold training. But there is no training for us, the administrators." (IR, Disability Activist)

These research results revealed that disability activists were confirmed to hold training both to increase employment opportunities in the formal and informal sectors and entrepreneurship. In carrying out their roles, disability activists do not act as trainers but help find institutions willing to provide training for PwDs.

III. Representational Role

Ife (2013) mentions that representational role means interactions with outsiders and to deal with the broader system for the benefit of the community or society. Meanwhile, Adi (2013) mentions this role as a broker, namely the ability to assist targets with available service sources according to target needs. Disability activists do this by partnering with other stakeholders and doing advocacy.

3.1 Partnering with Other Stakeholders

Disability activists perform this role by partnering with various parties such as local and national governments, private companies, and other non-profit organizations in carrying out activities that improve the welfare of the beneficiaries. They use networks at the regional and national levels to help open access to jobs or meet other needs.

"We help by using existing networks at the national and regional levels such as DKI Jakarta ... do we do synergy. Whether it is job information in the Jakarta area or other areas and provide training facilities." (IR, Disability Activist)

As an employer who supports the government and is committed to fulfilling the quota for PD workers. Alfamart collaborates with the PwDs community to disseminate information about job vacancies. Alfamart is a chain of supermarkets with many branches in Indonesia. These outlets generally sell a variety of food, beverage, and other living necessities. Alfamart said that recruitment information spreads more quickly through the community than other media.

"We recruit it faster through the community, because the news is conveyed more quickly, it spreads very quickly." (MA, Employer)

3.2 Advocate

Doing advocacy, namely, represents the community's interests to get a better deal or doing advocacy (Ife, 2013). Adi (2013) includes this ability in an advocate role, namely the ability to defend and become a representative who defends the target's interests. DMIF is active in advocating regarding the right to work for PwDs. In implementing this role, disability activists have discussed with Alfamart the requirements for applying for a job at Alfamart, which previously had a maximum age of 28 years now to 30 years with a minimum requirement of high school education. They also advocate for employers to have the appearance requirements removed from the job vacancy requirements for PwDs. When activists with disabilities find out that there are complaints from customers about crew stores with hearing disabilities, who do not answer when called, they advise that the store crew be given uniforms with deaf disabilities written and writing tools to facilitate communication.

"Alfamart's job requirements for the crew store are high school graduates, a maximum of 30 years. I used to have a maximum age of 28, experienced, so we recommend holding training. Like BRI, Telkom, they mostly accept friends with disabilities as telemarketing, like that. We advise removing the appearance requirements." (SB, Disability Activist)

DMIF, together with other organizations of persons with disabilities, are also active in conducting hearings with the government to promote policies that favor improving the welfare of persons with disabilities. One thing that continues to promote is infrastructure in government buildings become disability friendly. This advocacy role is the same as the OPD function proposed by WHO as a forum for PWD to unite in organizations to voice their rights to influence decision-makers in government and all sectors of society. (World Health Organization, 2010).

B. Obstacles Experienced by PWD in Accessing Work in the Formal Sector

Persons with disabilities have the same rights and opportunities to find work. Despite their limitations, there are still challenges or obstacles faced in accessing the right to work. ICF argues that two factors hinder PwDs participation in society: the environment and the personal (Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Disability in America, 2007). First, environmental factors, namely the factors that form the physical, social environment, and attitudes in which people live and carry out their lives, can become facilitators or obstacles. Second, personal factors are related to motivation and self-esteem, affecting how much a person participates in society. Other factors that affect this factor include gender, race, age, lifestyle, habits, social background, education, profession, characteristics, and other factors that impact individuals' disabilities.

1. Environmental Factors

Bampi, Guilhem, & Alves (2010) and Barnes (1996) stated that the inability of the environment to accept the condition of individuals with disabilities makes them unable to carry out their social functions.

1.1 Recruitment is not disability friendly.

The study results found that it was difficult for PwDs to find work because the job selection process was still not disability friendly. Employers provide an incomplete working requirement for applicants with disabilities, such as documents needed and a photograph and the lack of information about the job test to be carried out. Employer's HRD is also less responsive when the PD actively asks for the job selection process and the requirements that must be completed by the PD. It creates a misunderstanding because HRD employers think that potential PD job applicants ask too many questions. According to ILO (2013), it will not be a problem if the employer can specifically inform job requirements for workers with disabilities.

1.2 Acceptance of Work Only for Particular Disabilities

Employer policies are still discriminatory by only accepting specific mild physical disabilities, even though all PWD should be given equal opportunities.

Not all understand the meaning of inclusion. Inclusion is for all disabilities, not only specific disabilities but also job

vacancies and even civil servants' admission, which leads to only accepting physical disabilities. Even though there are many forms of disability, some cannot see, some are mental, there are various kinds of things. " (SB, Disability Activist)

According to HRD staff of Alfamart, they only accept specific disabilities because they do not have adequate facilities for other disabilities. They want to focus first on fixing the facilities to accept job applicants with all types of disabilities. The right to obtain decent work is the right of all persons, including workers with disabilities. However, there are still many job vacancies in the private sector and government that are not yet inclusive.

1.3 Education Qualifications for Work

Educational qualifications are still an obstacle for PWD to get a job. Meanwhile, the number of opportunities for PwDs to get an education is still limited. Therefore, for non-professional vacancies such as helping flower arrangements, therapists, or work that can be trained, it should not need high education because most PWD only graduates from elementary or special schools. Employers such as Alfamart, which has branches in Indonesia, include educational requirements for prospective employees of at least high school graduates.

"Our requirement is equal to high school. We need a person with calculating skills, both in the store and in the warehouse. They need the same skills if they become a cashier." (MA, Employer)

These skills are trainable and do not require high educational qualifications. When the higher education requirements are narrowed, the opportunity to work for PWD will be more significant.

1.4 Job Scams

The PwDs said there are still job vacancies that require them to pay for registration or administration if they want to be accepted for work. It is a problem because they do not have money and they want to work to earn money.

"So like this, when I apply for work. The employer asked for money so that I can be accepted in their office." (EN, Person with disabilities)

As job seekers need to be careful; sometimes, there are job vacancies that must pay to get a job. It is undoubtedly burdensome for job seekers, especially for disabled workers whose job opportunities are still rare.

1.5 Temporary Contract

Another obstacle that PwDs must face in accessing jobs is the outsourcing system or the contract system. Community workers say that employers accept PwDs only to comply with laws enforced by the government. Mostly, they only contracted PwDs for six months and end their contract. The law on outsourcing labor must also be changed so that the sustainability of PwD's work is more secure for them.

1.6 Accessible Facilities for Person with disabilities

The provision of disability-friendly work facilities is still an infliction for employers and hinders them in accepting disability workers. They must pay additional costs to build or remodel so that existing facilities match the needs of disabilities.

"Employers are afraid to accept PwDs in their office because they need to prepare accommodation that disability-friendly. From several companies that I met, it is indeed constrained by accommodation for PwDs. It is all about numbers for companies. They are thinking about how much it costs to renovate, for transportation, and others." (IR, Disability Activist)

SMERU Research Institute found, employers think they must spend an additional expense if they employ PwDs. PwDs still experience inaccessible workplaces for people with disabilities, both in private companies and government agencies, such as the absence of stairs for wheelchair users. Besides, the unavailability of space and facilities for wheelchair users has reduced job opportunities in the formal sector for physical disability. In the management of a disabled workforce, ILO (2013) suggests that employers must adjust to ensure that prospective workers with disabilities can carry out their work correctly.

1.7 Stigma from Employers

Employers already have a stigma about PWD, so they do not want to employ workers with disabilities. They see that the PwD's physical condition will prevent them from working like other employees. Disability activist said that if given the same opportunity as other individuals, PD can work well and eventually become HRD staff in charge of recruiting PD friends at Alfamart.

"I think the obstacles to getting a job are because employers see our physical condition. They thought that our work will be hampered and will not be the same as non-disabled employees. That is the obstacle." (DN, People with Disabilities)

This stigma can change when the company provides opportunities for PD workers to demonstrate their abilities and expertise.

"These friends inspire us. One person with disabilities in one shop or maybe in one office can inspire everyone around them. In addition to inspiration, they also teach other employees a sense of gratitude that they might not feel when friends with disabilities are not around. Moreover, of course, we learn to be patient because friends with disabilities need a particular need where the treatment is unique." (MA, Employer)

Employers can see that the PD is the same as other employees who can do their job well. PD can even become an inspiration for other employees because PD can still work enthusiastically and fulfill their duties as an employee

1.8 Lack of Support from Family

ILO (2013) said a lack of support and relationships from their family, friends, colleagues, and professionals affect the social life of PwDs. From the discussion results, the family still has a mindset that PwDs does not have the same abilities as other individuals. This condition is per that stated by Barnes, Oliver, & Barton (2002, p. 38), the family assumes that PD does not have to do something because it has an 'abnormal' body. Because the physical conditions are not the same as the others, the family provides excessive protection and thinks that PD will make things difficult for people around them. They should stay at home and not need to get an education. Even with high education, they think that in the end, PWD cannot work and compete with non-disabled workers. This condition follows the concept put forward by Chitereka (2010) that the family wants to protect PWD, not to let them make their own decisions without family supervision.

2. Personal Factors

Bampi, Guilhem, & Alves (2010) and Barnes (1996) stated that the inability of the environment to accept the condition of individuals with disabilities makes them unable to carry out their social functions.

1.1 Low Self-Confidence

They have limited physical or mental functions that impact their low self-confidence. In terms of mentality, this makes PwDs feel insecure and unwanted. They are still pessimistic even though the PwDs can match the qualifications required in a job vacancy. PWD thinks that they must have more abilities than non-disabled people so

that PD can be accepted to work. Besides, PD also feels pessimistic that they can do the job described in the job vacancy. In the end, this made PWD not dare to apply for a job and even gave up on working in the formal sector. Shakespeare (2006) in Chitereka (2010) describes a medical model that sees PD as an individual who cannot play a full role in society. This condition is per the explanation of Miles (2014), which states that PwDs are identical to unwanted people, so that they must have more abilities to work in the formal sector.

Their insecure attitude continues when they are working; they have difficulty making workplace adjustments. They do not want to mingle with other employees. It causes socializing barriers in the world of work, and PD cooperation with other colleagues does not go well. PD must actively communicate and be confident when chatting with other colleagues to interact with all workplace parties. It is essential to have positive thinking by not giving up, having a mental attitude toward work, and looking for motivational words.

1.2 Picky

Regarding personal facts, community workers say that PWD is still picky about jobs and see the salary offered when they share job vacancy information.

Yes, Pak Bandi often shared job opportunities in the WhatsApp group, but they often comment that I do not want. It is far. The salary is small. Sometimes I talk, the important thing is to work, get a salary and lawful.” (TU, People with Disabilities).

It is okay to be picky about work. However, the field findings show that friends with disabilities who are members of the DMIF community are still picky about jobs even though their education and experience are still minimal.

1.3 Distance

Also, distance is a challenge that dampens their motivation to apply for a job. It is an essential consideration for PwDs when applying for jobs or attending the training. Due to their disability, PwD relies on other people to apply for jobs and attend training. This condition follows the explanation of Kim & Canda (2006), where PwDs is more focused on disabilities where they need someone's help in carrying out social activities. Having a job close to home is more efficient and enjoyable, but not all job opportunities meet these criteria. Employers such as Alfamart said that companies try to place PD employees close to where they live but not all companies have many branches like Alfamart. Therefore, it needs PD who are brave and active to look for work in various opportunities.

V. CONCLUSION

DMIF is an organization for persons with disabilities providing inclusive services for all types of disabilities in Indonesia to be independent, and their welfare increases. Currently, DMIF focuses on providing training, distributing information on job vacancies, and other support needed by beneficiaries to improve their welfare.

Related to the disability activist efforts in opening the accessibility of disabled workers to the formal labor market, it turns out that it includes a facilitating role, an educational role, and a representational role. This research also found that employment barriers for persons with disabilities can range from personal to environmental factors. As Indonesia already ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, all the stakeholders must promote their rights. It is including the right to the opportunity to gain a living by work freely chosen or accepted in a labor market and work environment that is open, inclusive, and accessible to persons with disabilities. Disabled People's Organizations such as DMIF establish to ensure these rights are implemented in society and empower people with disabilities to channel their rights. Disability activist efforts also make sure they can perform their social roles within themselves, their immediate social environment, and society.

Finally, it is suggested that Government should provide employers, which hire PD employees, with financial assistance to build facilities for supporting accessibilities of PWD.

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